

The Impact of Transformational and Transactional Leadership, Organizational Culture, and Learning Organization toward Employee Satisfaction on ABC International School in Surabaya

Anggoro Kasih Dali

Abstract

Globalization has led industries, companies, and business to find ways to face the existing challenges. Adapting and analyzing current trends and situations is considered necessary and becoming one of the important aspects in organization. Government and its interventions are trying to balance the economy with policies while companies are trying to improve performance. ABC International School Surabaya is one of the most prestigious education providers in Surabaya Indonesia with the best education quality and professionals as teachers. Achieving company desired outcome while surviving the vast competition has led companies to improve internal human resources. This study aimed to analyze the effect of variable Transformational and Transactional Leadership, Organizational Culture, Learning Organization to achieve increase in Employee Satisfaction at the ABC International School Surabaya in Surabaya. The respondents of this research were 30 employees. For the process and analysing the data in this research is by using SPSS to get regression and statistical results. Based on the data from the questionnaires, among Transformational Leadership, Transactional Leadership, Organizational Culture, and Learning Organization has significant relationship to Employee Satisfaction. Among the dependent variables, Organizational Culture has proven to give a highest impact on Employee Satisfaction and companies need to work on how Organizational Culture can be managed properly.

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About Author (s)

Anggoro Kasih Dali, Widya Mandala Catholic University Surabaya, Indonesia.

Introduction

The trend of globalization and technological advancement is growing rapidly, the challenge of bringing the company forward and achieve the desired outcome is getting more and more difficult. Adapting to various business situations and conditions becoming significantly needed for organizations to be able to strive and compete (Chang and Lee, 2017). Many scholars emphasize that the success of a company is determined on the role of human resources. Human Resources plays a very important role in the scope of the company because employees are the foundation or key aspects of all of the company activities (Suyuthi, Hamzah & Payangan, 2014). Employee satisfaction cannot be solely measured with compensation and rewards they receive. Individual problems in the organization should get the attention of a leader. Effective leaders are leaders which recognizes the important powers embodied in the individual or group. These individuals can later become the basis for optimizing performance as well design a better organizational system. With the increasingly advanced technology and Internet usage, education has brought the advancement to education aspect into practice. ABC International School Surabaya has a commitment in providing the best and maximum education quality and service to maintain its recognition. This commitment is contained in the company's vision "Committed to provide the best quality education with excellence". To support this vision, ABC International School Surabaya has established strategies that set forth in the Company's Long-Term Plan which is evaluated every year once every 4 (four) years. The school realizes that society has a dynamic change on a view of education. Therefore, ABC International School Surabaya has manifests concern by organizing social and environmental awareness programs that touch various aspects community life, namely by carrying out Corporate Social activities Responsibility (CSR). This is done by providing free education in Community social activities, also profiding education and training programs CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) Program to companies and communities. Therefore, the researcher wants to analyze the influence of Transformational Leadership, Transactional Leadership, and Organizational Culture towards Learning Organization and Employee Satisfaction in ABC International School Surabaya, Surabaya. One of the competitive advantages of a company namely by developing employees. This further confirms that Employees are an important resource for any organization. It can be explained that business organization success. However, that doesn't mean good employees naturally show excellent performance as well. Kindly specifically, with increased employee academic background and job expectations, business administrators can increase employee job satisfaction by encourage employees, through leadership and work environment, namely through flexible and open atmosphere between leaders and employees (Chang and Lee, 2017). Robbins and Judge (2007) state that job satisfaction is caused by work environment, colleagues and superiors, compensation levels and employee opportunities for promotion. Enjoying the work itself with responsibility and the task he received became a strong reason in his relationship with job satisfaction. Meanwhile, the type of work that is interesting or work that challenging, providing a training program to support mastery work, freedom to work and use the potential that exists an individual is satisfied with his job. Miller et. al., (1991) states that leadership style has positive relationship to job satisfaction of employees. Research result Gruenberg (1980) obtained that the relationship is intimate and mutually helpful with colleagues and supervisors is very important and has a strong relationship with job satisfaction and has nothing to do with workplace conditions as well type of work. Path-Goal Theory (Evans, 1970; House, 1971; House & Mitchell, 1974 in Yukl, 1989) says that leaders encourage more performance by providing activities that affect their subordinates to believe that worthy results can be achieved with serious effort. Universally applicable leadership results in levels of performance and high subordinate satisfaction. (www.researchgate.net downloaded on the 25th November 2022). Based on the company profile, ABC International School Surabaya Surabaya provides a high quality education for students and prepare them for the future. This

school is one of the most well-known education providers in Surabaya and the employees can adapt their work position to their abilities and technique that the company has. In addition, they also feel their leader providing excellent & fair behavior to every employee, remuneration and the rewards given by the company to them are also assessed accordingly capabilities and work results of employees. It takes continuous strategy development to predict trends from the environment (Gardiner & Whiting, 1997). Senge (1990) proposed the importance of creating a learning organization. Various Business organizations are beginning to understand the fact that knowledge is a resource important for business organizations seeking to create core values. Aside from that used the core discipline of learning organization with an emphasis on accumulation knowledge and learning attitude. Also, through the "Fifth Discipline" proposed by Senge (1990), which performs the processing of dynamic thinking models for organization employees. With the ideas obtained from the learning organization then companies can increase the ability of business growth and innovation. Chang & Lee (2017) "Fifth Discipline" talks about how one needs to open up and change their insights, their perspective so that they are more effective in Responding to problems and challenges in work and career. The purpose of this learning organization has the good intention of intensifying the process transfer of knowledge between team members. In the learning organization (learning organization) the organization does not only learn from failures, but also learn successes from the past. (Bronner & Delaney, 2016). Danim (2015) suggests a learning organization from past failures and successes to spur people or people learners to do work or learning tasks well, creative and meaningful. The learning organization is a testing process experience continuously and the transformation of that experience into knowledge accessible to all members of the organization and relevant to main goal. The learning organization describes the learning environment, learning potential for work and learning environments in work contexts (Poell, Dam, & Berg, 2014).

ABC International School Surabaya is one of the implementing companies learning organization this is proven that every employee must always develop themselves in a sustainable manner. The school has a special unit in charge of training and education in charge of planning, implementing, and evaluate existing training programs. It is necessary to have an organizational culture within support learning organizations to acquire, improve and transfer pens knowledge easily according to what is needed by employees. Furthermore, efforts are needed to increase trust between administrators and employees, where these efforts will have a significant impact on whether learning organization can be successful or not (Gardiner & Whiting, 2017). Because organizational culture greatly influences the learning organization an important issue is seen namely by increasing the emphasis (Kasper 2011). Found that leadership, and organizational culture, influence each other and have a relationship important in developing a learning organization, and encouraging employees to use study facilities (Chang and Lee, 2017). According to Schein (1992), organizational culture is an archetype that is accepted by organization to act and solve problems, forming employees who able to adapt to the environment and unite the members organization. For this reason, it must be taught to employees, including employees who knew how to correctly examine, think and feel the problem faced. Employees who have understood the values in an organization will make these values te personality of the organization. Values and beliefs This will be manifested into their daily behavior at work, so it will be individual performance and each individual performance will lead to good organizational or employee performance as well. Could concluded that what is meant by organizational culture in this study is an organizational value system held by employees in the organization, which then influences the way the members work and behave organization (Cushway and Lodge, 2000). Anthony & Govindarajan (2013) states that every organization consists of elements or parts whose functions have been determined, for each

other cooperate and influence each other, and no one is more dominant or more the main part of the others, unless it must be coordinated in the goals that has been determined. There have been many studies on leadership skills discussed from various perspectives that have been carried out by researchers. Preliminary analysis about leadership is around the 1900s to 1950s, focuses attention on the differences in characteristics between leaders (leaders) and followers/employees (followers). Hence the results of research at the time of that period indicates that there is no single trait or combination characteristics or character that can fully explain the ability of para dreamer n, then the attention of the researchers shifted to the problem of the influence of the situation on the abilities and behavior of leaders. Subsequent studies of leadership have focused on the behavior that exhibited by effective leaders. In order to understand any factors that influence the behavior of effective leaders, the researchers using a contingency model. With a contingency model the researchers tested the relationship between personal traits, variables situation and leader effectiveness. Research in the 1970s and 1980s leading to the conclusion that leaders and leadership matter which is very important to learn (crucial), but these two things are realized as a very complex organizational component. Transactional and transformational leadership was developed by Bass (1985) departed from Maslow's opinion about the level of human needs. According to the theory of the hierarchy of needs, the needs of lower subordinates such as needs physically, a sense of security and hope can be fulfilled properly through application transactional leadership. However, self-actualization, according to him only possible to be fulfilled through the application of transformational leadership.

Literature review

Theoretical Basis

Transformational leadership

Transformational leadership has become one of the big topics to discuss and yet studied. According to Bass (2020), in transformational leadership, leaders must be capable in persuading the subordinates to perform their duties and carries out the tasks with the basis of for the sake of the organization. Ying (2019) also stated that transformational leaders convey a clear vision of the organization while stimulating its subordinates. To what extent a leader is called transformational can be measured in conjunction with the leader's effect on subordinates. Under a leader Transformational people feel trust, admiration, loyalty and respect towards those leaders and they are motivated to do those things more than the leader initially expected. Meanwhile, according to Bycio et. al., (1995) transactional leadership style is leadership style in which a leader focuses his attention on interpersonal transactions between leaders and employees that involve relationships exchange. The exchange is based on an agreement on classification goals, work standards, work assignments, and awards. A leader who must be responsive to change, able to analyze strengths and weakness of human resources so as to maximize performance organization and solve problems appropriately. Effective leaders can influence his followers to have greater optimism, a sense of self-confidence, and commitment to the goals and mission of the organization (Yukl, 1994). This matter brings consequences that every leader is obliged to provide earnest attention in building, moving and directing all potential employees in their environment in order to realize stability

Employee Satisfaction

Human life activities are different and one of the is how human traded their time for a job performed. A job or work is trade of between the time of a person and carry out the tasks provided. (As'ad, 2007). It is driven by the human desire to meet the needs that must be met. Job satisfaction is an atmosphere psychology of pleasant or unpleasant feelings towards their work (Davis & Keith, 1985). Meanwhile Porter and Lawler in Bavendam (2020) explained that

job satisfaction is a unidimensional block, where an employee would have something to be compared about to decide whether it's going to be a satisfaction or dissatisfaction with their job. Rashid (2015) defines satisfaction work as a reference for the effective orientation of an employee towards their role in the position they currently hold. Positive attitude towards Conceptually work can be expressed as job satisfaction and negative attitudes towards work equals dissatisfaction. This definition has got support from Smith and Kendall (1963) which explains that job satisfaction as an employee's feelings about his job. Simply put, jobs satisfaction can be interpreted as what makes people want and enjoy work. What makes them happy in their work or quit his job, according to Robin in Siahaan, E.E.

Learning Organization

Learning is the power to grow and individual learning is source of business growth. Chou (2013) argues that learning organization means the procedure by which knowledge is acquired and made to improve direction behavior. Heijden (2014) argues that learning organization is a type of inference from experience, which means the process of exploring and creating new knowledge, together with the systematic dissemination to include knowledge in organizations. Definition and learning organization that includes individuals, groups, and learning organization with efforts to increase stimulant learning for learning for organizations and individuals. This is a type of collective activity to achieve a shared organizational vision. However, the extent of learning from an organization actually depends on the ability to respond to rapidly changing environment (Kochan and Useem, 1992); (Matthews, 1994; Redding, 1997). In a learning organization team, members of the organization work together in a way that is different from the way conventional teams work but with trust each other and help each other achieve common goals and achieve achievements very well (Senge, 1990). Through the convergence of the five disciplines, it will be making learning organization into an innovation. Organizational Culture. Meek (1992) in Torrington and Hall (1995) argues that there is the relationship between culture and organizational effectiveness, and there are also assumptions that culture will unite all employees behind those goals has been set by the organization. Therefore, it often happens that management the organization will try to change or create a culture in the organization in order to achieve the achievement of organizational performance expected. Schein (1990) reveals that organizational culture consists of two concept layers, i.e. visible and invisible characteristics. Invisible layer among others, such as common values, norms, beliefs and business assumptions of members organization. While the layers look like company buildings, clothing, general behavior of employees, rules, stories, myths, language, and rituals. Culture Organizations have the ability to integrate day-to-day activities employees to achieve the planned goals, besides that it can help organization adapts well to the internal environment provide quick and appropriate responses (Daft, 2021). Robbins, (2020) explains that organizational culture is a value system that is held and carried out by members of the organization, so that This can differentiate the organization from other organizations.

Transactional Leadership

Pounder (2001) and Kim and Shim (2003) state that leadership transactional demand-oriented, with an emphasis on satisfaction basic and external of the request. Meanwhile, according to Bycio et. al. (1995) style Transactional leadership is a leadership style in which a leader focuses attention on interpersonal transactions between leaders and employees involving exchange relationships. Bass (1985) defines Transactional leadership is highly exchange-oriented, which means that Employees will only receive prizes if they show appropriate performance results with the goals outlined earlier, because of the tenets of leadership theory transactional is based solely on the operational relationship of giving and

accept between leaders and subordinates. Bass (1985) and other researchers suggest a theory of transactional leadership in a limited scope. The 4 types of transactional leadership styles are: Transactional Leadership is a contractual leadership between the leader and his followers. Leaders need followers and offer something in exchange for follower loyalty. Followers want to cooperate because there are things he is after as a reward. Meanwhile, work on may be not his personal goals, but rather the goals of the leader.

Transformational Leadership

The initial concept of transformational leadership was put forward by Burns (1978) which explains that this leadership style is a process where leaders and subordinates to achieve a level of morality and higher motivation. Transformational leaders try to elicit awareness of followers by setting higher ideals and moral values. Transformational leadership is divided into 4 dimensions, namely: idealized influence, intellectual stimulation, inspirational motivation, and individual consideration (Bass and Avolio, 1994): 1. Idealized influence the leader shows an acknowledgment, emphasizes trust, participates contributes to solving difficult problems, emphasizes the importance of goals, commitment and the ethical consequences of a decision. Several leaders admired as role models, they convey pride, loyalty, confidence, and achieving common goals. 2. Inspirational Motivation Leaders are good at calling out visions of the future, challenging the followers with high standards, speak optimistically and enthusiastically, and provide encouragement and meaning of what needs to be done. 3. Intellectual Stimulation Leaders question old assumptions, traditions and beliefs, stimulate new perspectives and ways of doing things and encourage the expression of ideas and reasons 4. Individual Consideration Leaders relate to others as individuals; take into account individual needs, wishes and aspirations; listen attentive; develop; recommend; and guide. Transformational leadership is characterized by paying attention development and change in the achievements of its followers, whether it becomes the better according to organizational criteria or not. Leader builds trust and support followers to express their full potential is inside him. Goals to be achieved between leaders and followers the same or similar, and run-in sync (Lensufie, 2020). Leadership style is how a leader implements his leadership function and how he is seen by those who try led or those who may be observing from the outside (Robert, 1992). Yukl (2019) defines leadership as a process of influencing others to understand and agree on what needs to be done and how to do it, and processes to facilitate individual effort and collectively to achieve a common goal. The leadership quality is considered an important factor in organizational success or failure to achieve its goals (Chen, 2022). The success of an organization is usually tied up with the success of a leader and vice versa. The role of leader becomes more and more the focus of study of researchers in the field of organizational behavior. Scheins (2002), emphasize that leaders have a very large influence on how organization achieve its purposes. Leaders play a key role in formulating and implementing the strategy implemented within the organizational (Su'ud, 2020). In the most recently published leadership theory, the type Leadership can be divided into transformational leadership and transactional (Burns, 1978; Bass, 1997).

The Effect of Transformational Leadership to Learning Organization

Leadership is an important factor that can influence learning organization. Leaders can improve the ability of learning organization through the delivery of leadership vision and learning opportunities or employees who created by leaders to provide opportunities for employees to improve learning organization (Edmondson, 2012; Gilley and Maycunich, 2010; Popper and Lipshitz, 2016). Lam (2012) conducted a cross-sectional study to investigate transformational leadership towards learning organization as well as demonstrating that transformational leadership can influence the process and achievements of the learning

organization. Leithwood et al (2017) argue transformational leadership can influence the increase in efficiency of learning organization.

H1 : Transformational Leadership has a significant effect on Learning Organization.

The Effect of Transactional Leadership to Learning Organization

Lee (2017) argues that some of the factors that better leadership impact the organization to learn, Thus, Leader will be able to create an organizational structure and shape the organizational culture to generate influence over a wide range of corporate affairs, actions and services; therefore, leadership really influences the learning organization. The effect of transactional leadership on the learning organization as well have significant relationships and organizations can improve the efficiency of Learning Organization through transactional leadership (Bass, 1997; Bass and Avolio 1990).

H2: Transactional Leadership has a significant effect on Learning Organization.

The Effect of Organizational Culture to Learning Organization

Influence between Organizational Culture on Learning Organization Garatte (1990) argues that organizations generally need to developing a learning organization, the previous administrators had to Demonstrate individual and team work learning abilities. Besides that, more needed to create a cultural climate for learning for the organization (Watkins and Marsick, 1993; Swimming, 2020; Hall, 2021). Based on the above literature can concluded that organizational culture has a significant positive effect on operation of learning organization. Daft (2019) also said organizational culture is an important feature for creating a learning organization with efforts to encourage organizations to be adapt to change.

H3: Organizational Culture has a significant effect on Learning Organization.

The Effect of Organizational Culture to Employee Satisfaction

The Effect of Transformational Leadership on Employee Satisfaction Robbins (2013) examines a manager who adopts a style Transformational Leadership will show high job satisfaction. So, concluded that Transformational Leadership has a significant relationship on employee job satisfaction.

H4: Transformational Leadership has a significant effect on Employee Satisfaction.

The Effect of Transactional Leadership on Employee Satisfaction

According to research by Koh et al. (1995) which confirms that Transactional leadership only emphasizes transactions that tend to be interpersonal relationship between leaders and members. This exchange is supported by the clarification of objectives, work standards, work assignments, and awards. This opinion is in line with Bass' opinion (1990) who argued that transactional leadership is the basis for ongoing organizational effectiveness. So, it is concluded that Transactional Leadership has a significant relationship to employee job satisfaction.

H5: Transactional Leadership has significant effect on Employee Satisfaction

The Effect of Organizational Culture on Employee Satisfaction

According to Huang dan Wu (2020) shows that Culture in organizations will have a significant impact towards organizational commitment and Employee Satisfaction. Robbins (1996) also argues that whenever an individual request the same as culture, it will produce the highest job satisfaction. Employees with higher level of autonomy will have the urge to produce better achievements and performance. Thus, higher satisfaction on what the employee earned within the organizational culture that the company provides. Based on several studies, it can be found significant results between organizational culture and job satisfaction.

H6: Organizational Culture has significant effect on Employee Satisfaction

The Effect of Learning Organization on Employee Satisfaction

Gardiner and Whiting (1997) show that research results in behavior resulting from organizational learning in response to external environment that can not only bring about an increase in performance organization, but also increase in employee satisfaction.

H7: Learning Organization has a significant effect on Employee Satisfaction

Research Model

Research Methodology

$$ES = b1.TFL + b2. TSL + b3. OC + b4. LO$$

$$LO = b5.TFL + b6. TSL + b7. OC$$

Data Analysis

The questionnaires provide a good measure of each instrument and results of the qualified respondents will be used in this research. This result will provide a better understanding of the phenomenon and yet, useful insight for the study. The respondents are all employees of ABC International School Surabaya.

Table 1. Multiple regression for Transformational Leadership, Transactional Leadership, Organizational Culture toward Learning Organization

		Coefficients ^a				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.718	.737		2.330	.028
	TFL	.336	.160	.269	2.102	.045
	TSL	-.549	.147	-.489	-3.733	.001
	OC	.831	.152	.786	5.454	.000

a. Dependent Variable: LO

Source: Processed Data (2022)

Based on the table provided, the regression value for each independent variable measure how significant an independent variable would affect the dependent variable. Transformational leadership has 0.269 regression value, this means that Transformational Leadership has 26.9% significance toward Learning Organization. While Transactional Leadership has a negative

regression value of 0.489, which means that this independent variable has a negative relationship toward the dependent variable. Organizational Culture has highest regression value at 0.786 toward Learning Organization. Which means that the independent variable has 78.6% impact on the dependent variable.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.046	.620		-.074	.941
	TFL	.418	.132	.336	3.165	.004
	TSL	-.200	.139	-.178	-1.435	.164
	OC	.367	.171	.348	2.153	.041
	LO	.427	.150	.427	2.845	.009

a. Dependent Variable: ES

Processed Data (2022)

Based on the table provided, the regression value for each independent variable measure how significant an independent variable would affect the dependent variable. Transformational leadership has 0.336 regression value, this means that Transformational Leadership has 33.6% significance toward Employee Satisfaction. While Transactional Leadership has a negative regression value of 0.178 toward Employee Satisfaction, which means that this independent variable has a negative relationship toward the dependent variable. Organizational Culture has highest regression value at 0.348 toward Employee Satisfaction. Which means that the independent variable has 34.8% impact on the dependent variable. Learning Organization has highest regression value at 0.427 toward Employee Satisfaction. Which means that the independent variable has 42.7% impact on the dependent variable.

Discussion

Based on the findings, we can conclude and draw some conclusions to provide a better understanding of the results. With regression value for each variable, the result of the first hypothesis which states "Transformational Leadership has a significant effect on Learning Organization" is a positive and significance effect. This is consistent with the study of Achmed (2012) which states that Transformational Leadership is crucial for learning organizational to increase. The result of the second hypothesis which states "Transactional Leadership has a significant effect on Learning Organization" is a positive and non-significance effect. This is aligned with the study of Malhotra (2015) where transactional leadership emphasize that work would not be valued only by rewards. The result of the third hypothesis which states "Organizational Culture has a significant effect on Learning Organization" is a positive and significance effect. This supports the study of Robbins (2017) where culture plays an important role in how organizations can learn and evolve into a better version of it. The result of the fourth hypothesis which states "Transformational Leadership has a significant effect on Employee Satisfaction" is a positive and significance effect. This supports the study of Schein (2019) where leadership correlates with satisfactions of followers. The result of the fifth hypothesis which states "Transactional Leadership has significant effect on Employee Satisfaction" is a positive and not significance effect. This means that transactional leadership has an impact on satisfaction due to the rewards the employees receive. The result of the sixth hypothesis which states "Organizational Culture has significant effect on Employee Satisfaction" is a positive and significance effect. This supports the study from Smith (2013) on how culture significantly affect employment satisfaction due to the environment and culture of an organizations. The result of the seventh hypothesis which states "Learning Organization has a significant effect on

Employee Satisfaction” is a positive and significance effect. This supports the findings of Chang (2020) where learning organizations will significantly affect satisfactions on employees.

Conclusion

The study provides a better understanding of the employee satisfaction in a school system in Surabaya. Thus, the variables discuss provides better insight into the understanding of leadership and culture toward learning organization and satisfaction of the employees. The research model in this study is developed to gain better understanding of how school should perform. Based on the results of data, we can draw some conclusions and implications, especially how to increase the satisfaction of employees. Based on the result, we can conclude that satisfaction is highly impacted by organizational culture, while transformational leadership does provide an impact toward satisfaction and transactional leadership has a negative relationship. While most schools focused on providing quality of education and branding, employees need to be focused on. Based on this study, managers should provide ways and media for improving teamwork and communication, provide the best measurements to measure employee’s performance, also encourage employees to appreciate other employees by establishing small group discussions in each department or cross departmental to discuss current issues. In a school system, each department is expected to achieve the agreed performance, while doing so, culture in each department needs to focused on, and also culture of the school as an organization. While transformational leadership also can be additional aspect to be discussed, managers should be a role model, take challenges, and also able to provide solution in each existing problem. Transformational leadership in school system can also provide changes in each individual, and also social system, where the relationship of leader and employees would also be more effective. This will create a valuable positive change in the followers with the end goal of transforming or developing followers into leaders. Transactional leadership is proven to have a negative relationship toward satisfaction, meaning in school system, employees are not solely work and finished their tasks for salary, pay, bonus, incentives, and other form of rewards. Further research can be done by adding another independent variable, such as dynamic capability, or knowledge management, to be able to understand better on learning organization and employee satisfaction.

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Appendix-1

TFL , TSL, OC toward LO

Model Summary^a

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.819 ^a	.671	.633	2334514130287

a. Predictors: (Constant), OC, TFL, TSL
 b. Dependent Variable: LO

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2.894	3	.965	17.701	.000 ^b
	Residual	1.417	26	.054		
	Total	4.311	29			

a. Dependent Variable: LO
 b. Predictors: (Constant), OC, TFL, TSL

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.718	.737		2.330	.028
	TFL	.336	.160	.269	2.102	.045
	TSL	-.549	.147	-.489	-3.733	.001
	OC	.831	.152	.786	5.454	.000

a. Dependent Variable: LO

TFL , TSL, OC, LO toward ES

Model Summary^a

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.903 ^a	.815	.785	1784568236730 72

a. Predictors: (Constant), LO, TSL, TFL, OC

b. Dependent Variable: ES

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	3.504	4	.876	27.505	.000 ^b
	Residual	.796	25	.032		
	Total	4.300	29			

a. Dependent Variable: ES

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.046	.620		-.074	.941
	TFL	.418	.132	.336	3.165	.004
	TSL	-.200	.139	-.178	-1.435	.164
	OC	.367	.171	.348	2.153	.041
	LO	.427	.150	.427	2.845	.009

a. Dependent Variable: ES

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